

TWO WAYS OF MESSAGE BLOCKS REARRANGEMENT TO PROTECT THE MESSAGE**Akram Naser Adam Mousa**

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ABSTRACT

An efficient, easy to implement and flexible method of message cryptography will be proposed. The method will enhance the speed of standard and chaotic methods of message cryptography by providing a good speed comparing with them. The method will provide a high level of security, it will use a private key of length equal 384 bits (for one round), this length will provide a key space capable to resist hacking attacks, and the decrypted message will be sensitive to the selected private key. The proposed method will be simple, it will use a simple chaotic logistic map model to generate the required secret keys, and it will use a simple message blocks-characters rearrangement to apply message encryption-decryption. The method will not alter the characters values, it will not need data conversion, and it will not require the complex of operations used in other methods, thus the program code will be minimized. The proposed method will flexible, it will provide the sender with the ability to change the number of rounds, the block size and the private key length, making these changes will not affect the encryption and decryption functions.

The proposed method will be implemented using various short and long messages, the following result analysis will be performed: Speed, quality and sensitivity, and the results will be used to prove that the proposed method will satisfy the requirement of good crypto method.

Keywords:

Cryptography, message, message block, reversing, rearrangement, PK, IK, CLMM.

INTRODUCTION

Encrypted text messaging as shown in figure 1 is a secure communication method that converts your messages into code [1-5]. This means that only the recipient with the correct decryption key can read them. It's a way to keep your conversations private and away from prying eyes, whether hackers, advertisers, or even government agencies [6-10]. Messages are encrypted to protect their content from unauthorized access. Encryption converts plain text into an unreadable (encrypted) form using a special algorithm, which can only be decrypted with a private key held by the intended recipient [11-15]. This ensures the confidentiality and privacy of information during transmission and storage.

Reasons for Encrypting Messages [16-20]:

- Protecting Sensitive Information: Messages containing personal, financial, or medical information are encrypted to ensure that no unauthorized person can access them[21-25].
- Privacy: Encryption protects users' privacy by preventing third parties, such as service providers or hackers, from accessing their message content [26-29].
- Security: If a message is intercepted by a third party, they will be unable to understand its content without the decryption key [30-33].
- Compliance with Laws and Regulations: Many organizations are required to encrypt data to meet privacy and security requirements [34-37].

- Trust: Encryption enhances trust between the sender and receiver, allowing them to feel secure that their information is protected [38-41].
- Message Encryption in Various Contexts: This can include emails, text messages, online conversations, and general data transmission.

Figure 1: Message crypto method diagram

The crypto method as shown in figure 1 contains two parts [42-45]: The sending part and the receiving part. The sending part uses the encryption function to process a source message and the private key to produce a cipher (encrypted) message, while the decryption part uses the decryption function to process the encrypted message and the PK to produce a decrypted message [46-50]. The crypto method will be classified as a good method if it meets the following requirements [51-55]:

- Quality: the encrypted message must be damaged and unreadable, it must have a low quality, and the quality parameters calculated between the source and the encrypted messages must satisfy the requirements listed in table 1 [56-60]. The decrypted message must be the same as the source message, and the quality parameters calculated between the source and the decrypted messages must satisfy the requirements listed in table 1.

Table 1: Quality parameters values requirements [61-66]

Quality parameter	Calculated between the source DCI and the encrypted DCI	Calculated between the source DCI and the decrypted DCI
Mean square error(MSE)	High	0
Peak signal to noise ratio(PSNR)	Low(<40)[80-84]	infinite
Correlation coefficient(r)	Low(<0.2)[80-84]	1

- Speed: the method must provide a high speed of encryption-decryption, it must optimize both the encryption and decryption times [67-70].
- Security: The method must provide a high level of security. The PK must be long, and the length of the PK (≥ 128 bits) [71-77] must provide a huge key space capable to resist hacking attacks, the decrypted message must be sensitive to the selected PK, the sender and the receiver must use the same PK, any minor changes made by the receiver must be considered as a hacking attempt by producing a damaged message [78-84].

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- Simplicity: The method must use simple procedure for key generation, message encryption and message decryption [77-80].
- Flexibility: The method must be efficiently used process short and long messages, the method must provide the sender with the ability to change the number of rounds, the block size and the PK length, making these changes must not affect the encryption and decryption functions.

The objective of this research paper is to produce a method of message cryptography, which will satisfy the above mentioned requirements.

RELATED WORKS:

A lot of methods were produced for message cryptography, some of these methods were based on standard methods such as DES and AES methods [1-10], other methods were based on chaotic principles and they were used to enhance the speed of existing standard methods [77-84]. Standard based method are the mostly spreaded methods, they were used to encrypt-decrypt short messages, and these methods became slow when dealing with long messages [11-15]. Standard based methods share some features, some of these features required enhancement, and these features include:

- Message blocking: Message is to be divided into blocks, the block size is small, thus an extra time will be needed to apply message blocking and blocks combining, the block size is fixed and cannot be changed by the message sender. The presented method will use message blocking, the block size is variable and it can be changed by the message sender.
- PK length: Standard method use fixed length PK, the length varies from short to long, the message sender cannot change the PK length. The presented method will use a variable PK length, the length will depend on the number of selected rounds, and it can be changed by the message sender.
- Security: The standard methods provide a security level, which ranges from poor to strong, depending on the used length of the PK. The presented method will increase the security level to very strong by using a very long length of the PK, figure 2 shows the provided key spaces for various methods.

DES key space:

$$= 2^{56}$$

$$= 72057594037927936 \text{ combinations}$$

AES key space:

$$= 2^{256}$$

$$= 1.1579208923731619542357098500869 \times 10^{77} \text{ combinations}$$

Presented method key space (using one round):

$$= 2^{384}$$

$$= 3.9402006196394479212279040100144 \times 10^{115} \text{ combinations}$$

Figure 2: Key spaces for various methods

- Speed: Standard methods are slow especially when they use long messages. The presented method will speed up the process of message cryptography and it will be efficient when processing short and long messages.
- Number of rounds: Standard method use a fixed number of rounds, all rounds must be executed, rounds are dependent and all rounds process the same message block. The presented method will use multiple rounds, rounds are independent, each round will process the whole message, and the number of rounds can be selected by the message sender.
- Characters altering: In standard methods characters values must be converted to binary [22-30], these values will be processed using a complicated sequence of operations, the values will be altered. The presented method will not alter the values of the message characters, the encryption-decryption process will be applied by using simple characters positions rearrangement.

The existing method usually convert the message to binary, and the binary version will be treated, The presented method will treat the decimal values.

- Simplicity: Standard method are not simple, they use a complicated sequence of operations to apply key generation and message characters processing. The presented method will be simple, it will use a simple chaotic logistic map model (CLMM) [80-84] to generate the required secret keys, and it will use a simple rearrangement operation to apply message encryption-decryption.
- Flexibility: Standard methods are not flexible, the presented method will be flexible, it will allow the message sender to change the number of rounds, the block size and the PK length, and these changes will not affect the encryption and decryption functions.

THE PRESENTED METHOD

The presented method is a variable block size, variable PK length and variable number of rounds. The number of rounds will be selected by the message sender, and each round is an independent processing unit. In the encryption phase the round uses the part of the PK and the input message as shown in figure 3 to perform the following tasks:

Figure 3: Encryption round

- Rounds two indices (IK) keys generation.
- Using the first IK to rearrange the message blocks.
- Reversing the obtained message.
- Using the second IK to rearrange the characters of the reversed message.

In the decryption phase the round uses the part of the PK and the input message as shown in figure 4 to perform the following tasks:

- Generating two IKs,
- Using the second IK to rearrange the message.
- Reverse the message.
- Rearrange the message using the first IK.

Figure 4: Decryption round

The PK for each round as shown in figure 5 will contain the following components:

NBS=10;NBE=8;

rs=3.77;xs=0.11;

re=3.77;xe=0.11;

Figure 5: PK example

NBS: The value of this parameter will determine the number of blocks to be used to divide the message from the starting position and it will be used to calculate the block size (BS).

NBE: The value of this parameter will determine the number of blocks to be used to divide the message from the end position (reversed message) and it will be used to calculate the block size (BS).

rs and xs: Chaotic logistic parameters to be used to generate the first IK.

re and xe: Chaotic logistic parameters to be used to generate the second IK.

IK GENERATION

Indices key (IK) is an array of unsigned integer unrepeated values, and it can be obtained by sorting a data set, the first element in IK points to the smallest element in the data set, the second element points to the next smallest element in the data set and so on.

The proposed method will use a chaotic logistic map models (CLMM) [77-84] to generate the required IKs. The method will use two IKs for each round, IK1 and IK2; IK1 will be used to rearrange the message blocks obtained by blocking the message from the starting position, while the IK2 will be used to rearrange the message blocks obtained by blocking the message from the end position.

The CLMM will use the values of a chaotic logistic parameters r and x and the value of the number of blocks NB, the CLMM shown in figure 6 was executed to generate an IK with 15 elements (see figure 7):

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```

%Chaotic logistic parameters:
r1=3.77;x1=0.11;
%CLMM:
for i=1:15
x1=x1*r1*(1-x1); %Chaotic logistic equation
cds(i)=x1;
end
[cdss IK1]=sort(cds);
IK1 =
    9    5    1    3    7    15   13   11   10   12   14    6    2    4    8
    
```

Figure 6: Used chaotic logistic parameters to generate an IK

Figure 7: Plot of the generated IK

The generated IK is very sensitive to the selected values of the CLMM parameters, any changes in the values of these parameters will lead to change the generated IK. To show this, the following three cases were used to generate the IK using the PK components shown in figure 6, figures 8 and 9 show the obtained IKs, and here it is seen that the IKs were changed.

Case1: r1 was changed from 3.77 to 3.775.

Case 2: x1 was changed from 0.11 to 0.118.

Case 3:r1 was changed from 3.77 to 3.771 and x1 was changed from 0.11 to 0.112.

```

IK1 = Case 1
    14    9    5    1    3   12    7   15   10    6   11    2    4    8   13
IK2 = Case 2
    7    3   12   10   14    1    5    8    4   13    9   11   15    2    6
IK3 = Case 3
    9   14    5    1    3    7   12   10   11   15    6    2    4   13    8
    
```

Figure 8: Obtained IKs after doing the changes

Figure 9: Plots of the obtained IKs

MESSAGE BLOCKING

Message blocking means dividing the message into equal blocks, this operation is needed in the presented method to minimize the IK generation time. One of the disadvantages of using CLMM to generate secret key is the key generation time. The key generation time will rapidly increased when increasing the key length, for example the message with length equal 100 characters (short message) will require an indices key with length equal 100 to be used to rearrange the message characters, the key generation time will equal 0.004000 seconds, while the key generation time required to rearranged a message with length equal 100000 characters (long message) will equal 11.977000 seconds.

Message block size will be variable and it will be selected by the sender and for each characters (blocks) rearrangement operation, the block size (BS) will be within range 1 (no blocking, number of blocks (NB) will equal message length (L) to L. Message blocking some times leads to create a fragment in the message(remaining part), the length of this fragment will range from 0 to BS-1, this fragment will be kept without rearrangement (see figures 11 and 12), so to encrypt this fragment the obtained message must reversed (see figure 10) and rearrange again.

Message cryptography using two ways of message blocking

```

L=length(m);
for i=1:L
    m1(L)=m(i);
    L=L-1;
end
    
```

gnikcolb egassem fo syaw owt gnisu yhpargotpyrc egasseM

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Figure 10: Message reversing example

Figure 11: Message blocking

```

m='Message cryptography using two ways of message blocking';
L=length(m)
NB=8;
BS=fix(L/NB)
r1=3.77;x1=0.11;
for i=1:NB
    x1=x1*r1*(1-x1);
    ds1(i)=x1;
end
[dss1 IK]=sort(ds1)
IK =
    5  1  3  7  6  2  4  8
e=m;
for i=1:NB
    c=IK(i);
    e(1,(i-1)*BS+1:(i-1)*BS+BS)=m(1,(c-1)*BS+1:(c-1)*BS+BS);
end
e =
    ng twoMessagrapof mes ways e cryphy usisage blocking
    
```

**Remaining part
7 characters**

Figure 12: Remaining part in the encrypted message remained the same as in the source message

The message blocks in the encryption phase will be rearranged using the associated IK, and it will be implemented as follows:

For each block with index i, the output block with index i will be replaced by the input block with index c, where c is the content of IK with index i (see figure 13 as an example).

The message blocks in the decryption phase will be rearranged using the associated IK, and it will be implemented as follows:

For each block with index i, the output block with index c will be replaced by the input block with index i, where c is the content of IK with index i (see figure 13 as an example).

Figure 13: Message blocks rearrangement

Message encryption function

This function will be called to implement one round of encryption (see figure 3), and figure 14 shows the contents of this function:

```

function [me]=MES_EF(m,NB1,NB2,r1,x1,r2,x2)
L=length(m);
BS1=fix(L/NB1);
BS2=fix(L/NB2);
for i=1:NB1
  x1=x1*r1*(1-x1);
  ds1(i)=x1;
end
[dss1 IKS]=sort(ds1);
for i=1:NB2
  x2=x2*r2*(1-x2);
  ds2(i)=x2;
end
[dss2 IKE]=sort(ds2);
em1=m;
for i=1:NB1
  c=IKS(i);
  em1(1,(i-1)*BS1+1:(i-1)*BS1+BS1)=m(1,(c-1)*BS1+1:(c-1)*BS1+BS1);
end
for i=1:L
  em2(L)=em1(i);
  L=L-1;
end
me=em2;
for i=1:NB2
  c=IKE(i);
  me(1,(i-1)*BS2+1:(i-1)*BS2+BS2)=em2(1,(c-1)*BS2+1:(c-1)*BS2+BS2);
end
end

```

Figure 14: Message encryption function

Message decryption function

This function will be called to implement one round of decryption (see figure 4), and figure 15 shows the contents of this function:

```
function [dm]=MES_DF(m,NB1,NB2,r1,x1,r2,x2)
L=length(m);
BS1=fix(L/NB1);
BS2=fix(L/NB2);
for i=1:NB1
    x1=x1*r1*(1-x1);
    ds1(i)=x1;
end
[dss1 IKS]=sort(ds1);
for i=1:NB2
    x2=x2*r2*(1-x2);
    ds2(i)=x2;
end
[dss2 IKE]=sort(ds2);
dm1=m;
for i=1:NB2
    c=IKE(i);
    dm1(1,(c-1)*BS2+1:(c-1)*BS2+BS2)=m(1,(i-1)*BS2+1:(i-1)*BS2+BS2);
end
dm2=dm1;
for i=1:L
    dm2(L)=dm1(i);
    L=L-1;
end
dm=dm2;
for i=1:NB1
    c=IKS(i);
    dm(1,(c-1)*BS1+1:(c-1)*BS1+BS1)=dm2(1,(i-1)*BS1+1:(i-1)*BS1+BS1);
end
end
```

Figure 15: Message decryption function

Implementation and results discussion

The speed of the presented method was examined. To see the effects of message blocking and the message length, a set of short messages ($L < 1$ K characters) were selected and processed without blocking ($NB=L$) and using the PK shown in figure 16, the encryption (decryption) time and the encryption speed were calculated and table 2 shows the obtained speed results:

```
L=length(m);
NBS=L;NBE=L;
rs=3.77;xs=0.11;
re=3.77;xe=0.11;
```

Figure 16: Used PK1

Table 2: Speed results for short messages without blocking

Message length (character)	Encryption time(second)	Encryption speed (K characters per second)
25	0.0100	2.4414
37	0.0070	5.1618
55	0.0070	7.6730
120	0.0080	14.6484

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200	0.0090	21.7014
500	0.0150	32.5521
750	0.0240	30.5176
900	0.0340	25.8502
Average	0.0143	17.5682

The same messages were processed using the presented method and with message blocking, the PK shown in figure 17 was used and table 3 shows the obtained speed results:

**NBS=12;NBE=15;
rs=3.77;xs=0.11;
re=3.77;xe=0.11;**

*Figure 17: Used PK2***Table 3: Speed results for short messages with blocking**

Message length (character)	Encryption time(second)	Encryption speed (K characters per second)
25	0.0070	3.4877
37	0.0070	5.1618
55	0.0070	7.6730
120	0.0070	16.7411
200	0.0070	27.9018
500	0.0070	69.7545
750	0.0070	104.6317
900	0.0080	109.8633
Average	0.0071	43.1519

From tables 2 and 3 the following can be seen:

- The message blocking way of encryption for short messages has a results closed to the speed results of message encryption without blocking, so the message can be considered as a short message if the message length is less than 200 characters, this message can be treated without blocking.
- The method gave a good speed results, the encryption time slowly increased when increasing the message length and the encryption speed rapidly increased when increasing the message length.

A set of long messages were selected and the PK shown in figure 18 was used to process these messages and table 4 shows the obtained speed results:

**NBS=100;NBE=120;
rs=3.77;xs=0.11;
re=3.77;xe=0.11;**

*Figure 18: Used PK3***Table 4: Speed results for long messages with blocking**

Message length (K characters)	Encryption time(second)	Encryption speed (K characters per second)
1	0.0070	142.8571
5	0.0080	625.0000
10	0.0090	1111.1
15	0.0100	1500.0
25	0.0100	2500.0
50	0.0120	4166.7

75	0.0150	5000.0
100	0.0170	5882.4
Average	0.0110	2616.0

From table 4 the following can be seen:

- The presented method provided a good speed results, the average encryption speed was high and was equal 2616.0 K characters per second.
- The encryption time grew slowly when increasing the message length.
- The encryption speed grew rapidly when increasing the message length.
- The presented method enhanced the speed of other existing method and it provided a significant speed up as shown in table 5.

Table 5: Speed up of the presented method

Method	Encryption speed (K samples per second)	Speed up (times)
Standard Based methods		
DES	010.6	246.7925
3DES	9.2	284.3478
AES	11.1	235.6757
RC2	7.6	344.2105
RC6	19.1	136.9634
BF	68.7	38.0786
Chaotic based methods		
Chaotic [79]	141.2305	18.5229
Hyper chaotic [79]	636.3379	4.1110
Introduced in [80]	888.8867	2.9430
Introduced in [81]	911.0352	2.8715
Introduced in [82]	638.4082	4.0977
Introduced in [83]	360.4102	7.2584
Introduced in [84]	384.9609	6.7955
Presented method		
Proposed in this paper method	2616.0	1.0000

The presented method required a small memory space size; this size was ranged from 2136 bytes for a message of 1 K characters to 204888 bytes for a message of 100 K characters.

The quality of the proposed method was examined, the obtained encrypted messages were always damaged, while the obtained decrypted messages were always the same as the source messages, and to prove the fact that the proposed method satisfies the quality requirements, a set of messages were selected and the quality parameters values between the source message and the associated encrypted one were calculated, and table 6 shows the obtained results:

Table 6: Quality parameters results

Message length (K characters)	MSE	PSNR	r
1	11184	17.6026	0.0248
5	10945	17.8186	-0.0114
10	10867	17.8906	-0.0080
15	11050	17.7236	-0.0172
25	10809	17.9442	0.0037
50	10741	18.0075	0.0037
75	10821	17.9327	0.000688

100	10773	17.9770	0.0046
Remarks	High	Low	Low

The obtained low values of PSNRs and low values of r , and the high values of MSEs shown in table 6 prove that the proposed method satisfied the quality requirements of good crypto method.

The proposed method is very sensitive to the selected PK, the message receiver must use the same PK selected by the sender, any minor changes made the receiver in the PK will be considered as a hacking attempt by producing a damaged decrypted message, and to show this the message: 'Message cryptography using two ways of message blocking' was encrypted using the PK shown in figure 19, the encrypted message was decrypted by applying each of the following case changes in the PK, table 7 shows the obtained decrypted messages :

L=length(m);
NBS=L;NBE=L;
rs=3.77;xs=0.11;
re=3.77;xe=0.11;

Figure 19: Used PK

- Case 1: No changes.
- Case 2: NBS was changed to 8.
- Case 3: NBE was changed to 6.
- Case 4: re was changed to 3.78.
- Case 5: xr was changed to 0.12.
- Case 6:re was changed to 3.79.
- Case 7: xe was changed to 0.10

Table 7: Obtained decrypted message

Case	Decrypted message
1	Message cryptography using two ways of message blocking
2	l anno s aw hscistgtygrfkyse rwsscao ngaopeiuMpeoy gbg
3	Mshn se creosgeoip asgwmyggesbykgo saacf i latyrpo tnuw
4	ct rkew Mlggy suwhasa spseoa tresggoo nsginaibomfcgpey
5	tppggu gilny sgt oihyoo eacswayrm ckssen fsaMoegsewbr a
6	soermagtu ssls n epp fbregt acynsMewsawoiahyoogckgi
7	le wagsMgeofrotnmineseski grag pytgocsawpho y usbas cy

The obtained damaged decrypted messages showed the proposed method sensitivity.

CONCLUSION

A simple and easy to implement method of message cryptography was presented, the method used a simple chaotic logistic map model to generate the required indices keys, a simple message blocks-characters rearrangement, it did not alter the characters values, and did not use data conversion, a simple rearrangement operation was used to replace the complex of operations required for other existing methods of message cryptography. The proposed method was efficient, it increased the level of security by using a long private key, and it enhanced the speed of message cryptography by providing a significant speed up comparing with the speeds of other existing methods. The proposed method used multiple variable rounds, variable block size, and variable private key length, the message sender defines these parameters, and changing them did not require any changes in the method encryption and decryption functions. Each round was used as an independent processing unit to apply two ways of message blocks-characters rearrangement, from the message starting position and from the message end position. The proposed method was efficient when using short and long messages, short messages with length less than 200 characters were processed efficiently with or without message blocking. Message blocking was used to optimize the method when processing long messages.

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The proposed method was implemented using various short and long messages and the obtained results were used to study the speed, quality and sensitivity, and the studies results showed that the proposed method satisfied the requirements of good crypto method.

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